

relatively fast compared with sunn hemp and dhaincha. Every kilogram of P applied at 13 kg/ha produced 108 kg grain in cowpea, 85 in dhaincha, 89 in

sunn hemp, and 67 in fallow plots, showing an increase of 18-41 kg grain/kg P over fallow plots (see table).

Green manuring saved about 13 kg P/

ha and contributed to extra grain yield. Cowpea was the best green manure crop for rice. ■

Crop management

Effect of tillage on physical properties of soil and yield of peanut in a rice-based cropping system

P. P. Prasadini, C. N. Rao, S. R. Rao, and M. S. Rao, Soil Physical Conditions Improvement Project, Andhra Pradesh Agricultural University, Hyderabad, India

Farmers in southern India, particularly in Andhra Pradesh, grow peanut after wet season puddled rice. In the rhizosphere, peanut requires a physical environment entirely different from that of rice. Inadequate peanut seedbed preparation in puddled soils results in poor germination, plant stand, growth, and yield.

We studied the effect of five tillage methods (see table) for irrigated peanut after puddled rice during 1988-89 and 1989-90 wet seasons. The experiment

was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications in a sandy loam soil with 0.11% organic C.

Plowing was deeper in the tractor-drawn treatment. Mean weight diameter (MWD) of seed zone aggregates varied among the tillage treatments. MWD, with many clods, was highest with the country plow. The rototiller treatment had small and relatively uniform aggregates.

Tillage affected germination. It was highest with the rototiller, where aggregate sizes favored good seed-soil contact and the highest soil moisture content. Soil penetration resistance recorded at pegging stage was least in the rototiller treatment. Haulm and pod yields were highest in the tractor-drawn treatment, closely followed by those with the rototiller.

The higher yields obtained with tractor tillage compared with bullock-drawn treatments might be due to the deeper plowing, which resulted in breaking of

the subsoil hardpan layer and smaller aggregates. Higher yields with rototillage were due to uniform aggregate size and low soil strength (penetration resistance).

We suggest that farmers use rototillage when growing peanut after puddled rice in light-textured soils because of the relative ease of operation, low cost, and higher yields. ■

Effect of tillage on physical properties of soil and yield of peanut. Hyderabad, India, 1988 and 1989.

Treatment	Plowing depth (cm)	Mean weight diameter (cm)	Soil moisture ^a (% wt/wt)	Germination (%)	Penetration resistance at pegging stage (kg/cm ²)	Yield (t/ha)	
						Haulm	Pod
T1 Plowing twice with bullock-drawn, country plow	7.0	4.5	7.4	47	35	2.39	1.44
T1 + disc harrow twice, bullock drawn	7.1	3.0	7.9	51	33	2.52	1.45
T1 + disc harrow 4 times, bullock drawn	7.8	2.3	7.2	52	35	2.54	1.70
T1 + rototiller twice, power tiller drawn	7.6	1.6	11.3	57	29	3.13	1.90
T5 Disc plow once + disc harrow once, tractor drawn	12.9	3.0	10.7	55	31	3.20	1.96
LSD (0.05)	-	-	1.3	6	1	0.35	0.11

^aSoil moisture at 20 d after sowing.

Evaluation of rice planting methods for rainfed lowlands of Karnataka

V. V. Angadi, P. N. Umapathy, G. D. Radder, S. K. Nadaf, and B. M. Chittapur, Agricultural Research Station, University of Agricultural Sciences, Mugad 580007, Dharwad, Karnataka, India

Rice is normally sown with a seed drill in the rainfed lowlands of interior Karnataka. Sowing dry seed on moist soil with the onset of the monsoon (DSR-moist) is the common practice, with dry sowing on dry soil (DSR-dry) seen in some areas. Wet sowing can be difficult

Grain yield and net profit as influenced by planting methods of rice in rainfed lowlands of Karnataka, India, 1990 and 1991 kharifs.^a

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)		Net profit (\$/ha)	
	1990	1991	1990	1991
Wet sown without fertilizer	4.3	F	10.7	F
Wet sown with fertilizer	5.6	F	13.6	F
Dry sown without fertilizer	N	4.5	N	14.5
Dry sown with fertilizer	5.2	6.1	12.4	21.2
Line transplanted with fertilizer	5.0	5.6	10.8	17.2
Broadcast pre-germinated seeds with fertilizer	1.8	F	0.9	F
LSD (0.05)	1.2	1.3		

^aN = treatment not included, F = failed treatment.

in years when the monsoon comes early and the rain is heavy.

We evaluated different planting methods for establishing rice in rainfed lowlands during 1990 and 1991 kharif. Treatments included DSR-moist and DSR-dry with and without fertilizer on puddled soil, line transplanting (TPR), and broadcasting pregerminated seeds (WSR) under puddled conditions. The trial was laid out in randomized block design with four replications on a clay soil with pH 7.4, 0.74% organic C, 36 kg available P/ha, and 228 kg available K/ha.

For the fertilized treatments, 100-22-41 kg NPK/ha was applied. P and K were broadcast before sowing or transplanting, and N was applied in three equal splits at 20 and 40 d after sowing and just before panicle initiation. Abhilash was the test variety.

DSR-dry was done on 18 May 1990 and 13 May 1991; DSR-moist on 29 May 1990 and 4 Jun 1991; TPR on 19 Jul 1990 and 16 Jul 1991; WSR on 19 Jul 1990 and 14 Jun 1991.

The monsoon started on 26 May 1990 and 30 May 1991 with total rainfall of 1,038 mm in 1990 and 1,265 mm in

1991. Rainfall of 1990 was closer to average for the area (950 mm) than that of 1991, which was 33% more than the average. Excessive rains after sowing led to failure of DSR-moist and WSR because seeds were submerged and subjected to anoxic conditions.

Dry sowing in dry soil produced higher, more stable grain yields and higher net profit than the other planting methods (see table). With the clay soils of the region, however, methods of dry soil preparation are needed to facilitate early establishment of DSR. ■

Integrated pest management—diseases

Maintenance of *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn, the causal agent of rice sheath blight (ShB), in gum flakes

N. I. Singh and R. K. T. Devi, Botany and Plant Pathology Department, Manipur Agricultural College, Iroisemba, Imphal 795001, India

Fungal cultures have been maintained for several years in sterile distilled water, soil, liquid nitrogen, by freeze drying, and by deep freezing. We developed a simple method that allows workers to maintain large numbers of fungal cultures under limited resources and space.

In the method, 3- × 1-inch glass slides were cleaned to make them grease-free, rinsed in ethanol, and air-dried. Two to three drops of 1% dextrose were put in the middle of the slide. Either a sclerotium or a fungal bit taken from an actively growing culture was placed in

the dextrose solution. The slides were placed in sterile petri dishes lined with moist filter papers and then incubated at 25 ± 1 °C for 96 h for sclerotial germination or ramification of mycelium.

A few drops of Camel Adhelin (a synthetic gum manufactured by Camlin Pvt. Ltd., Bombay 400059, India) that had been autoclaved at 15 lb pressure for 15 min were poured over the mycelium on the slides. When the slides were dried at 25 °C, thin flakes formed with the fungus firmly embedded in them. We eased these flakes off the slides with a sterile blade and stored them in small sterile vials. Gum-free slides with fungal growth served as control. The fungus was

also maintained on potato dextrose agar (PDA) (5 ml/test tube, 120 × 15 mm). Each treatment was replicated 10 times.

The viability of *R. solani* was tested monthly after 6 mo of storage by transferring it to PDA. A culture was recorded as nonviable if it did not grow after repeated transfers.

R. solani had 5-99% viability in the three substrates (see table). Subcultures obtained from the gum flake grew slowly at first compared with those maintained in other substrates and periodically transferred. This slow growth may be due to the time required for the gum flake to soften and for dormant mycelium to be activated by the moisture present in the medium. ■

Viability of *R. solani* maintained in various substrates.

Substrate	Duration of survival	
	mo	%
Gum flake	38	99
Gum-free slide with fungal growth	7	10
Potato dextrose agar slant	18	5

A new assessment key for leaf blast (BI)

H. O. Pinnschmidt and P. S. Teng, IRRI; J. M. Bonman, Du Pont, Newark, Delaware, USA; and J. Kranz, University of Giessen, Germany

A flexible key for leaf BI assessment has been designed for quantitative epidemiological and host-pathogen interaction studies. The key takes into account leaf BI severity and the stratification of lesion type. It uses lesion size and appearance as criteria to characterize the lesions.

Typical lesions are spindle-shaped, with varying length, width, and length:width ratio. Lesion area can be

approximated by the formula

$$F = \frac{W}{15} (6L + 8 \sqrt{((W^2 + L^2)/4)})$$

where F = lesion area (mm²), L = lesion length (mm), and W = lesion width (mm). From this equation, we developed a diagram that divides susceptible type lesions into five size classes on an exponential scale. The L:W ratio of lesions varied within each class while the lesion area remained the same (see figure). Resistant type lesions (not shown in figure) were assumed to cover an area of 0.25 mm².